

Curvature Invariants as Generators of a Geometric Field Structure

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We developed a curvature-based variational framework for localized configurations of a two-dimensional curved substrate. The geometry is described through invariants of the configuration tensor, in particular the mean curvature H and the curvature deviator D . The associated Euler–Lagrange equations are derived under prescribed geometric constraints.

The quadratic curvature structure is analyzed to identify the parameter regime in which the functional is bounded from below and the resulting fourth-order surface equation is elliptic, ensuring structural well-posedness of the variational problem.

Embedding the configurational field into three-dimensional space yields a Maxwell-type structure in which distinct curvature invariants generate different field modalities. The formulation provides a unified geometric setting in which mass-like and charge-like behavior of space arise as structurally different curvature modes of a single field.

Keywords: curvature invariants, geometric variational methods, Euler-Lagrange equations, curvature deviator, ellipticity, coercivity, fourth-order surface equations, geometric field theory

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1. Introduction

Unified field theory seeks a common theoretical framework for describing the fundamental interactions. Geometric approaches have played a central role in this pursuit, beginning with Einstein’s formulation of general relativity [1]. Shortly thereafter, Weyl proposed a geometrical extension aimed at unifying gravitation and electromagnetism [2,3], in which the gravitational limit recovers general relativity while the electromagnetic sector is structurally related to Maxwell’s theory [4]. Higher-dimensional constructions such as Kaluza–Klein theory [5,6] and later developments within string theory [7] have continued to explore unification through geometric generalization. Other unification schemes, including electroweak constructions [8], further illustrate the central role of geometry in modern theoretical physics.

Recent developments in geometric formulations of field theory emphasise that familiar physical structures can emerge from the underlying differential geometry:

gauge-theoretic constructions can recover classical electromagnetism from geometric principles [9], while metric-affine and Weyl-type extensions clarify how non-metricity, torsion and curvature enter modified gravity and related field models [10,11].

The present work adopts a different perspective. Rather than extending space-time dimension or introducing additional gauge structure, we consider a variational framework in which curvature invariants of a two-dimensional geometric substrate constitute the fundamental quantities. The construction is inspired by models developed in membrane biophysics, where the shape of membrane-enclosed entities is determined by the minimization of curvature-dependent elastic energies under geometrical constraints such as fixed area and volume [12]. Extensions incorporating in-plane anisotropy [13] and statistical mechanical treatments based on curvature patches [14,15] have provided a mathematically controlled setting for analyzing equilibrium shapes. Numerical methods for solving the corresponding variational problems have been developed and refined [16,14,15,17,18].

Since these models are formulated in the language of differential geometry, their variational structure can be abstracted from the biological context and interpreted more generally as a curvature-based geometric framework. In this work we formulate such a framework and analyze its structural properties.

2. Localized configurations of a two-dimensional curved substrate

We describe space as a thin curved surface and identify highly curved localized regions (buds) of this surface. The space is considered connected (shedding off of a bud to become a free entity is not included). The mean curvature and the curvature deviator characterize distinct modalities of surface curvature, providing a geometric basis for interpreting different interaction sectors within a unified framework.

2.1. Geometric formulation of the surface model

We consider a smooth oriented surface $\Sigma \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ representing the two-dimensional space field. The surface in a three dimensional space is described by an embedding $\mathbf{X} : U \subset \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$, with local coordinates (u^1, u^2) .

The induced metric (first fundamental form) on Σ is

$$g_{ab} = \partial_a \mathbf{X} \cdot \partial_b \mathbf{X}. \quad (1)$$

Indices $a, b, c \in \{1, 2\}$ label the local coordinates on the surface, and repeated indices imply summation over this range.

The unit normal vector field \mathbf{n} defines the second fundamental form

$$b_{ab} = \partial_a \partial_b \mathbf{X} \cdot \mathbf{n}. \quad (2)$$

The shape operator (Weingarten map) is

$$S^a{}_b = g^{ac} b_{bc}, \quad (3)$$

whose eigenvalues are the principal curvatures C_1 and C_2 . The curvature invariants are

$$H = \frac{C_1 + C_2}{2}, \quad K = C_1 C_2, \quad D = \frac{|C_1 - C_2|}{2}. \quad (4)$$

The configuration tensor is defined invariantly as the deviation of the shape operator \underline{C} from a prescribed reference operator \underline{C}_0 ,

$$\underline{M} = \underline{C} - \underline{C}_0. \quad (5)$$

In a principal curvature basis,

$$\underline{C} = \begin{pmatrix} C_1 & 0 \\ 0 & C_2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \underline{C}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} C_{1,0} & 0 \\ 0 & C_{2,0} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

If the principal directions of \underline{C} are rotated relative to those of \underline{C}_0 by an angle ϕ , then in the reference basis

$$\underline{M} = \underline{R} \underline{C} \underline{R}^{-1} - \underline{C}_0, \quad (7)$$

where

$$\underline{R} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \phi & -\sin \phi \\ \sin \phi & \cos \phi \end{pmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

Symmetry and isotropy. The energy density depends on the mismatch tensor $\underline{M} = \underline{R} \underline{C} \underline{R}^{-1} - \underline{C}_0$, where $\underline{R}(\phi)$ is an in-surface rotation and \underline{C}_0 is a prescribed reference curvature operator. The functional is invariant under simultaneous in-surface rotations of both \underline{C} and \underline{C}_0 , i.e. under $\underline{C} \mapsto \underline{R} \underline{C} \underline{R}^{-1}$, $\underline{C}_0 \mapsto \underline{R} \underline{C}_0 \underline{R}^{-1}$ for any $\underline{R} \in SO(2)$. In this sense the model remains isotropic at the level of the geometric construction. However, if \underline{C}_0 possesses distinct principal values $C_{1,0} \neq C_{2,0}$, it defines a preferred in-surface axis and therefore introduces material anisotropy. The special case $C_{1,0} = C_{2,0}$ recovers full in-surface rotational symmetry. The angular dependence $\cos(2\phi)$ appearing in the decomposed form reflects relative in-surface orientation between \underline{C} and \underline{C}_0 .

The shape of a bud corresponds to a stationary point of the curvature mismatch functional \mathcal{C}_M ,

$$\mathcal{C}_M = \int \frac{d\mathcal{C}_M}{dA} dA \quad (9)$$

whose area density is expressed in terms of invariants of \underline{M} ,

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_M}{dA} = w_i \text{Tr}^2 \underline{M} + w_a \text{Det} \underline{M}, \quad (10)$$

where w_i weights the trace (umbilic) sector and w_a weights the determinant/deviatoric sector. Integration is performed over the closed surface with area $A = 4\pi R_s^2$, where R_s is a constant with dimensions of length (meter). The surface encloses the volume $V = 4\pi R_s^3/3$.

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Performing the necessary calculations and using the relation

$$C_1 C_2 = H^2 - D^2, \quad (11)$$

the curvature mismatch functional density $d\mathcal{C}_M/dA$ becomes

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_M}{dA} = (4w_i + w_a)(H - H_0)^2 - w_a (D^2 - DD_0 \cos(2\phi) + D_0^2). \quad (12)$$

We introduce dimensionless curvatures h and d , $h = HR_s$ and $d = DR_s$, dimensionless area and volume elements,

$$da = \frac{dA}{4\pi R_s^2}, \quad v = \frac{3V}{4\pi R_s^3}, \quad (13)$$

and normalize curvature mismatch functional density with respect to $(4w_i + w_a)$ to yield

$$\frac{dc_M}{da} = ((h - h_0)^2 - w_d (d^2 - dd_0 \cos(2\phi) + d_0^2)), \quad (14)$$

and

$$c_M = \oint ((h - h_0)^2 - w_d (d^2 - dd_0 \cos(2\phi) + d_0^2)) da, \quad (15)$$

with $w_d = w_a/(4w_i + w_a)$. Integration is performed over the dimensionless surface area $a = 1$. We define the averaged dimensionless curvature invariants as

$$\langle h \rangle = \oint h da, \quad \langle d \rangle = \oint d da, \quad (16)$$

where integration is performed over the entire dimensionless area $a = 1$. Global thermodynamic equilibrium corresponds to zero variation of the curvature mismatch functional,

$$\delta c_M = 0, \quad (17)$$

at given geometric constraints: fixed dimensionless area

$$\oint da = 1, \quad (18)$$

fixed volume v ,

$$\oint dv = v, \quad (19)$$

and fixed average curvature tensor invariants

$$\oint h da = \langle h \rangle_0, \quad (20)$$

and

$$\oint d da = \langle d \rangle_0. \quad (21)$$

2.2. Axisymmetric reduction

We now restrict the analysis to axisymmetric surfaces. The surface is parametrized by the meridional arc-length l and the angle ψ describing the orientation of the meridian, following [15]. The parametrization derivation is described in Appendix A.2 (Derivation of the axisymmetric parametrization). In this representation the coordinates normalized by R_s are

$$\mathbf{r}(l, \varphi) = (r(l) \cos \varphi, r(l) \sin \varphi, z(l)), \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{dr}{dl} = \cos \psi, \quad \frac{dz}{dl} = \sin \psi. \quad (23)$$

dimensionless principal curvatures are

$$c_1 = \frac{\sin \psi}{r}, \quad c_2 = \frac{d\psi}{dl} \equiv \psi_l, \quad (24)$$

and dimensionless area and volume elements are

$$da = \frac{1}{2} r dl, \quad dv = \frac{3}{4} r^2 \sin \psi dl. \quad (25)$$

We take into account the local constraint following from the parametrization (Eq.(23)),

$$\cos \psi = r_l. \quad (26)$$

Using this parametrization, the dimensionless curvature mismatch functional can be written in the form

$$c_M = \oint \mathcal{L} dl, \quad (27)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L} = & \frac{1}{8} \left[\left(\frac{\sin \psi}{r} + \psi_l - \frac{h_0}{2} \right)^2 - w_d \left(\frac{\sin \psi}{r} - \psi_l \right)^2 \right] r \\ & + \frac{w_d}{8} \left[2 \left(\frac{\sin \psi}{r} - \psi_l \right) d_0 \cos(2\phi) - d_0^2 \right] r - \frac{1}{2} \lambda_a r - \lambda_v \frac{3}{4} r^2 \sin \psi \\ & - \frac{\lambda_h}{4} \left(\frac{\sin \psi}{r} + \psi_l \right) r - \frac{\lambda_d}{4} \left(\frac{\sin \psi}{r} - \psi_l \right) r - \lambda (\cos \psi - r_l), \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

and λ is a local Lagrange multiplier that enforces the parametrization constraint (26).

The variational problem is expressed by the Euler–Lagrange equations

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial r} - \frac{d}{dl} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial r_l} \right) = 0, \quad (29)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \psi} - \frac{d}{dl} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \psi_l} \right) = 0. \quad (30)$$

Euler-Lagrange equations are further developed in the Appendix.

2.3. Quadratic curvature kernel and coercivity

Motivation To understand the structural properties of the variational problem, we first study the highest-order quadratic kernel of the normalized curvature mismatch functional density dc_M/da . This determines which curvature modes are penalised at leading order and identifies the parameter regime in which the principal part of c_M is bounded from below (coercive). Such coercivity governs ellipticity of the associated fourth-order operator and is a necessary condition for structural well-posedness of the Euler–Lagrange system.

This subsection isolates the highest-order quadratic curvature kernel that governs the principal part of the functional c_M (27). The shape-selecting shifts induced by the terms including h_0 and d_0 (and in particular by the coupling $d d_0 \cos(2\phi)$) are addressed at the level of the full Euler–Lagrange equations. Here we focus exclusively on the highest-order quadratic structure.

Quadratic kernel and curvature modes.

Starting from the normalized curvature mismatch functional density dc_M/da curvature density (12), we isolate the leading quadratic part of the expression for the energy by setting $h_0 = 0$ and $d_0 = 0$ and discarding constant and lower-order terms. This yields the principal quadratic form

$$\mathcal{Q} = (4w_i + w_a) h^2 - w_a d^2. \quad (31)$$

Using the definitions of h and d by c_1 and c_2 we obtain

$$\mathcal{Q}(c_1, c_2) = \frac{4w_i + w_a}{4} (c_1 + c_2)^2 - \frac{w_a}{4} (c_1 - c_2)^2. \quad (32)$$

The kernel (Eq.32) diagonalises in two orthogonal curvature modes: the *isotropic* mode $c_1 = c_2$ and the *traceless deviatoric* mode $c_1 = -c_2$.

The corresponding eigenvalues

$$\lambda_+ = \frac{4w_i + w_a}{4}, \quad \lambda_- = -\frac{w_a}{4}. \quad (33)$$

represent the "effective stiffnesses" of the two quadratic curvature mismatch terms (with respect to the corresponding principal curvature modes). When both eigenvalues are positive, the quadratic form is positive definite and provides coercive quadratic control of curvature perturbations.

Gauss–Bonnet and independence of invariants.

According to the Gauss–Bonnet theorem, integration of Gaussian curvature

$$c_1 c_2 = h^2 - d^2 = k \quad (34)$$

over the entire surface with constant topology, yields a constant, which is characteristic for the topology. $\int_{\Sigma} k \, dA$ is constant. Hence, the structural independence of the quadratic invariants arises once reference terms that are linear in h and d are included.

Positivity and coercivity The quadratic kernel (Eq.(32)) is positive definite in the curvature variables if and only if both eigenvalues are positive,

$$\lambda_+ > 0, \quad \lambda_- > 0, \quad (35)$$

i.e.

$$4w_i + w_a > 0, \quad w_a < 0. \quad (36)$$

Equivalently,

$$-4w_i < w_a < 0. \quad (37)$$

Within Eq.(37), both isotropic and deviatoric curvature modes are penalised and the quadratic kernel is coercive in (h, d) .

At the parameter value where $\lambda_- = 0$, the quadratic curvature mismatch functional loses "stiffness" in the corresponding curvature mode and the quadratic kernel becomes degenerate.

For $w_a = 0$, the model reduces to the Helfrich/Willmore model [19,20]. For $w_a > 0$ one has $\lambda_- < 0$, so the quadratic form becomes indefinite and loses coercivity in the deviatoric mode. In this regime equilibrium shapes arise only through the balance with geometric constraints and lower-order or reference terms.

Interpretation of the deviatoric term

The contribution $(c_1 - c_2)^2$ isolates the magnitude of the principal-curvature mismatch and measures departure from umbilicity without selecting a preferred in-surface direction. For $w_a < 0$ it strengthens coercivity at quadratic level; for $w_a > 0$ it is destabilising in the precise sense that the quadratic kernel is indefinite.

Coercivity of the quadratic curvature mismatch kernel ensures that the curvature mismatch functional c_M is bounded from below in the curvature variables and provides control of the highest-order terms in the variational problem. In particular, positive definiteness of the kernel implies ellipticity of the associated fourth-order Euler-Lagrange operator. Ellipticity guarantees structural well-posedness and regularity of solutions [21] but does not by itself establish stability of specific equilibria, which depends additionally on lower-order terms and imposed constraints. Thus coercivity is a structural prerequisite for existence theory, whereas the equilibrium of particular shapes is a finer, solution-dependent property.

2.4. Order and ellipticity of the Euler-Lagrange system

Motivation Having identified the quadratic curvature kernel, we now examine the differential order and ellipticity of the resulting Euler-Lagrange system. Ellipticity of the principal operator ensures that the geometric field equation is structurally well posed and that high-frequency perturbations are penalised. This provides the analytic foundation for interpreting equilibrium shapes as stable geometric configurations.

Order of the Euler–Lagrange system The curvature mismatch functional density (Eq.(14) depends on the principal curvatures c_1, c_2 , which are second derivatives of the embedding \mathbf{X} (cf. (2)–(3)). Since the functional is quadratic in curvature, the first variation introduces two additional derivatives. Consequently, the Euler–Lagrange system is fourth order in the embedding \mathbf{X} .

This fourth order refers to derivatives of the surface position, not to powers of curvature invariants. In the axisymmetric reduction, the introduction of the auxiliary angle ψ lowers the apparent order of the reduced equations: curvature involves first derivatives of ψ over the arclength l , and the resulting equation contains the second derivative of ψ over l . Because ψ itself represents a first derivative of the profile, the reduced system is equivalent to a fourth–order equation for the embedding.

Linearised principal operator and ellipticity Let \mathbf{X}_* be a smooth reference embedding and consider a normal variation $\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{X}_* + \eta \mathbf{n}_*$, where η is a scalar displacement field describing a small normal deformation of the surface Σ . The analysis below corresponds to the linearisation of the Euler–Lagrange equations around the reference surface, assuming the deformation amplitude η to be small.

To the leading order in η , $\delta C_i \sim \nabla_\Sigma^2 \eta$, so the quadratic kernel Q (Eq.(32)) generates at leading order a quadratic form in second derivatives of η . The linearised Euler–Lagrange operator therefore has the principal part [22]

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{prin}} \eta \sim \alpha \Delta_\Sigma^2 \eta, \quad (38)$$

where Δ_Σ is the Laplace–Beltrami operator and α is a constant determined by the quadratic curvature kernel Q (Eq.(32)), equivalently by the eigenvalues λ_\pm .

In a local Fourier representation, $\eta \sim e^{ik \cdot x}$, where k denotes the local wave vector of the Fourier mode. Here $\sigma(k)$ denotes the principal symbol of the linearised operator evaluated at the Fourier mode k . In this representation derivatives act as multiplication by ik , so the highest–order derivative terms determine the principal symbol of the operator, $\sigma(k) \sim \alpha |k|^4$.

The operator is elliptic (strongly elliptic) if $\alpha > 0$ [21], which is ensured by positivity of the quadratic kernel Q (Eq.(32)), i.e. Eq.(36) (or equivalently Eq.(37)).

If $w_a > 0$, the negative eigenvalue λ_- implies that the quadratic kernel Q (Eq.(32)) is not positive definite, and the principal symbol $\sigma(k)$ is no longer positive definite. In that case the purely quadratic part of the functional (28) does not provide coercive control in the deviatoric mode; regularisation then depends on global constraints and lower–order or reference terms.

The ellipticity condition ensures structural well–posedness of the fourth–order geometric field equation. Stability of particular equilibria further depends on lower–order terms and imposed constraints.

In the axisymmetric reduction (Appendix A), the highest-derivative term involves only the mean-curvature mode (proportional to w_i), whereas the full surface ellipticity condition is determined by the quadratic kernel eigenvalues λ_{\pm} .

The numerical results presented in Figure 1 correspond to the case $w_a = 0$ (equivalently $w_d = 0$ in the system (28) - (30)) [19,20]. Detailed numerical exploration of the cases with ($w_a \neq 0$) is left for future work.

An illustrative axisymmetric equilibrium shape obtained by solving the constrained variational problem using the predictor-corrector algorithm [15] is shown in Figure 1. Mean curvature h and curvature deviator d are depicted by colors.

Some features of the $(v, \langle h \rangle, \langle d \rangle)$ phase diagram of equilibrium closed shapes have been presented in [24]. In the model, elementary particles can be described by considering a small bud on a bigger quasi-spherical closed shape (a shape with $v \simeq 1$). The bigger globule has both principal curvatures positive while the bud is connected to the mother-sphere by a neck in which $\sin \psi \geq 0$, but ψ_l and consequently the Gaussian curvature $c_1 c_2$ changes sign at the root of the neck. We outline only the part over the boundary where $c_1 c_2$ becomes negative (Figure 1(a)-(h)).

3. The field as a consequence of space curvature

3.1. Three-dimensional field representation

The curvature invariants defined on the two-dimensional surface can be connected to an effective field in the embedding space. We introduce a vector field \mathbf{P} defined in \mathbb{R}^3 such that its divergence reproduces an averaged curvature invariant,

$$\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{P} - \mathbf{P}_0) = \langle \mathfrak{N} \rangle, \quad (39)$$

where $\langle \mathfrak{N} \rangle$ denotes a prescribed averaged invariant of the configuration tensor and \mathbf{P}_0 corresponds to the inherent (reference) field.

The averaged invariant $\langle \mathfrak{N} \rangle$ can be interpreted as a source density whose spatial extension into \mathbb{R}^3 is encoded through the divergence of \mathbf{P} . In this way intrinsic curvature concentrations act as effective sources of the ambient field.

Introducing a companion kinetic field \mathbf{K} allows one to construct a coupled first-order system whose structure is formally analogous to Maxwell-Heaviside equations. This provides a dynamical embedding of curvature into three-dimensional space.

3.2. Waves of the unified space field

To derive the wave equation for the field \mathbf{P} we follow the Maxwell-Heaviside construction [25]. For convenience of scaling, we introduce a field proportional to \mathbf{P} ,

$$\mathbf{P} = \varepsilon \mathbf{p}, \quad (40)$$

where ε is interpreted as the permittivity of space [26].

Fig. 1. Axisymmetric equilibrium shape of the surface bud obtained by solving the variational problem in the isotropic sector ($w_d = 0$, $d_0 = 0$). Panels (a)–(d) show the same numerical solution with curvature-invariant fields visualised on the surface: (a) shape; (b) mean curvature on the convex region represented by the red color; (c) mean curvature on the concave region represented by the blue color; (d) curvature deviator represented by the yellow color. Panels (e)–(h) provide a simplified representation based on region-wise averages, with boundaries indicated where the Gaussian curvature $K = C_1 C_2$ changes sign. Panels (i)–(l) show a further geometric idealisation retaining the averaged invariants. The parameters of the entire shape given in panels (a)–(h) are $v = 0.95$, $\langle h \rangle = 1.022$, $h_0 = 0$, $w_d = 0$, and $d_0 = 0$. Source data are available in Ref. [23].

We introduce a companion kinetic field \mathbf{K} satisfying

$$\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}_0) = 0, \quad (41)$$

and define

$$\mathbf{K} = \mu \boldsymbol{\kappa}, \quad (42)$$

where μ is a proportionality constant (kinetic permeability) and \mathbf{K}_0 denotes the baseline kinetic field.

The vortex equations are postulated in analogy with Maxwell's equations:

$$\nabla \times (\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_0) = -\frac{\partial(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}_0)}{\partial t}, \quad (43)$$

$$\nabla \times (\boldsymbol{\kappa} - \boldsymbol{\kappa}_0) = \mathbf{j} + \frac{\partial(\mathbf{P} - \mathbf{P}_0)}{\partial t}. \quad (44)$$

Here \mathbf{j} represents an effective current density associated with curvature transport.

Source-free case. Assume there are no curvature buds, so that

$$\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{P} - \mathbf{P}_0) = 0, \quad (45)$$

and

$$\mathbf{j} = 0. \quad (46)$$

Taking the curl of Eq. (43) and using the vector identity

$$\nabla \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{A}) = \nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}) - \nabla^2 \mathbf{A}, \quad (47)$$

together with Eq. (45), yields

$$\nabla^2(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_0) = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \nabla \times (\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}_0). \quad (48)$$

Using Eq. (44) with $\mathbf{j} = 0$ and the constitutive relations (40)–(42), we obtain

$$\nabla^2(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_0) = \varepsilon\mu \frac{\partial^2(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_0)}{\partial t^2}. \quad (49)$$

An analogous calculation gives

$$\nabla^2(\boldsymbol{\kappa} - \boldsymbol{\kappa}_0) = \varepsilon\mu \frac{\partial^2(\boldsymbol{\kappa} - \boldsymbol{\kappa}_0)}{\partial t^2}. \quad (50)$$

These equations admit plane-wave solutions,

$$\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{p}_0 + \Delta\mathbf{p} \sin(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} - \omega t + \delta_{\mathbf{p}}), \quad (51)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\kappa} = \boldsymbol{\kappa}_0 + \Delta\boldsymbol{\kappa} \sin(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} - \omega t + \delta_{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}), \quad (52)$$

where \mathbf{k} is the wave vector, ω the angular frequency, and the propagation velocity is

$$c = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\varepsilon\mu}}. \quad (53)$$

4. Dimensional analysis

The dimension of curvature is $1/\text{m}$. It follows from Eq. (39) that the field \mathbf{P} is dimensionless. From Eq. (44) the dimension of $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ is m/s . From Eq. (41) the field \mathbf{K} has dimension $1/\text{s}$. Using Eq. (43), dimensional consistency requires that the dimension of \mathbf{p} is m/s^2 , representing acceleration. Using Eqs. (40) and (42) also yields the dimensions of the proportionality constants ε (s^2/m) and μ ($1/\text{m}$), respectively. It can be verified using Eq. (53) that the velocity has the dimension m/s . The dimensions of mass (kg) and charge (As) are not involved in the model.

5. Gravito-kinetic and electromagnetic fields: permittivity and permeability

To relate the dimensionless curvature field \mathbf{P} introduced above to physically measurable gravito-kinetic and electromagnetic quantities, we introduce proportionality mappings to the corresponding physical fields. We write

$$\mathbf{G} = \gamma_G \mathbf{P}, \quad \mathbf{D} = \gamma_D \mathbf{P}, \quad (54)$$

where \mathbf{G} denotes the gravito-kinetic field and \mathbf{D} the electric displacement field. The constants γ_G and γ_D serve as unit-setting parameters that connect the geometric field to physical observables.

The physical fields satisfy the divergence relations [26,25]

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{G} = \rho_m, \quad \nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} = \rho_q, \quad (55)$$

where

$$\rho_m = \frac{dm}{dV}, \quad \rho_q = \frac{dq}{dV}, \quad (56)$$

denote the mass and charge densities, respectively.

Within the present curvature framework, mass and charge are associated with averaged curvature invariants according to

$$m = \lambda_m \langle D \rangle V, \quad q = \lambda_q \langle H \rangle V, \quad (57)$$

where λ_m and λ_q are dimensional constants fixing the physical units, $\lambda_m = \text{kg}/\text{m}^2$ and $\lambda_q = \text{As}/\text{m}^2$. Using the constitutive relation $\mathbf{P} = \varepsilon \mathbf{p}$ and the wave-velocity expression

$$c = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\varepsilon \mu}}, \quad (58)$$

the parameters ε and μ are the effective permittivity and permeability constants.

For the gravito-kinetic sector, the corresponding effective permittivity is estimated as [27]

$$\varepsilon_G = 1.193 \times 10^9 \text{ s}^2/\text{m}. \quad (59)$$

For the electromagnetic sector, the permittivity of vacuum is

$$\varepsilon_0 = 8.9 \times 10^{-12} \text{ s}^2/\text{m}. \quad (60)$$

The difference between the two values spans approximately twenty orders of magnitude.

Assuming that disturbances in both sectors propagate with the same characteristic velocity c (identified with the speed of light), the corresponding permeability parameters follow from Eq.(53),

$$\mu = \frac{1}{\varepsilon c^2}, \quad (61)$$

yielding

$$\mu_G \approx 10^{-26} \text{ m}^{-1}, \quad \mu_0 \approx 1.26 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}. \quad (62)$$

6. Discussion

The interpretation of curvature invariants as physically meaningful quantities may be viewed in analogy with membrane theories in which in-plane order, anisotropic spontaneous curvature, or active stresses couple directly to the local curvature tensor and thereby determine the mechanical response of the surface [28,29,30,31,32]. In such systems, scalar and tensorial curvature invariants are not merely geometric descriptors but effective fields encoding interactions, elastic moduli, and symmetry breaking.

By abstracting this variational structure to a two-dimensional space substrate, the present framework associates mass-like and charge-like behavior with the invariants D and H , respectively. The resulting formulation provides a unified geometric setting in which gravitational-type and electromagnetic-type effects are represented as different curvature modalities of a single space field. In this sense, the unification achieved here is essentially structural.

Several theoretical approaches recast gravitational dynamics in a Maxwell-Heaviside form. In gravitoelectromagnetism (GEM), tidal tensors and post-Newtonian expansions yield effective electric and magnetic fields while preserving the matter sources of general relativity [33,34]. The resemblance between the present construction and GEM is therefore formal: GEM arises as an approximation within general relativity, whereas here, field-like behavior emerges from the curvature functional of a two-dimensional space field. The distinction lies in replacing external sources by geometric quantities derived from curvature invariants.

Stationary configurations correspond to constrained equilibria of the curvature functional, and distinct entities are associated with different regions of the $(v, \langle h \rangle, \langle d \rangle)$ phase diagram [24]. This viewpoint does not eliminate the standard mass-charge description, but reinterprets it as an emergent representation of underlying geometric invariants.

The difference between gravitational and electromagnetic sectors is attributed to distinct curvature modalities: mass-like behavior is associated with the average deviator $\langle D \rangle$, while charge-like behavior is associated with the averaged mean curvature $\langle H \rangle$. Unlike the Gaussian curvature, which integrates to a topological invariant for closed surfaces, $\langle H \rangle$ and $\langle D \rangle$ encode local geometric anisotropy and therefore serve as dynamically relevant quantities. The linear deviatoric term, originally introduced in membrane elasticity to describe lateral anisotropy [13,15], plays a central role in this geometric interpretation.

The Maxwell-Heaviside-type representation of the field provides a dynamical description of perturbations of the curvature field in the embedding space. The effective permittivity and permeability parameters introduced in this representation are determined by matching with measured gravitational and electromagnetic phenomena. Their large numerical disparity reflects the different effective coupling strengths of the corresponding curvature modes. The present model does not derive these constants from first principles; rather, it provides a geometric framework in

which such constants acquire interpretation in terms of curvature scaling parameters.

All quantities in the model are expressed using the fundamental dimensions of length and time. Conventional units such as kg and A enter only through the identification of curvature invariants with physical observables. A detailed confrontation with experimental data lies beyond the scope of this work, but the framework suggests that mass and charge may be regarded as emergent manifestations of geometric structure rather than independent fundamental attributes.

Appendix A. Euler–Lagrange equations in the axisymmetric formulation

In this appendix, we derive the Euler–Lagrange (EL) equations corresponding to the functional \mathcal{L} (Eq.(27)) for the axisymmetric shapes. The procedure follows the standard reduction used in curvature-based membrane models (cf. [15]).

A.1. Derivation of the axisymmetric parametrization

We refer to the distances normalized by R_s . An axisymmetric surface is obtained by revolving a planar meridional curve $\gamma : l \mapsto (r(l), z(l))$ about the z -axis. Using the azimuthal angle $\phi \in [0, 2\pi)$, the embedding is

$$\mathbf{r}(l, \phi) = (r(l) \cos \phi, r(l) \sin \phi, z(l)). \quad (\text{A.1})$$

We choose l as the arc-length along the meridian (see Fig. 2), so that

$$r_l^2 + z_l^2 = 1, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where $(\cdot)_l \equiv d(\cdot)/dl$ and introduce the angle $\psi(l)$ by parameterizing the unit meridional tangent as

$$\mathbf{t}_m = (r_l, z_l) = (\cos \psi, \sin \psi), \quad (\text{A.3})$$

so that (A.2) is satisfied identically and

$$r_l = \cos \psi, \quad z_l = \sin \psi. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

The principal curvatures are

$$c_1 = \frac{\sin \psi}{r}, \quad c_2 = \psi_l, \quad (\text{A.5})$$

and the curvature invariants

$$h = \frac{c_1 + c_2}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\sin \psi}{r} + \psi_l \right), \quad d = \frac{c_1 - c_2}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\sin \psi}{r} - \psi_l \right). \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Fig. 2. parametrization of the surface. Left: side view, right: top view. The contour meridian curve is described by the arc-length parameter l , with radial coordinate $r(l)$ and tangent angle $\psi(l)$ measured with respect to the outward radial direction. Rotation around the symmetry axis z is described by the azimuthal angle ϕ .

A.2. Axisymmetric Lagrangian

The Lagrange function that defines the variational problem follows from Eq.(28)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2} [(h - h_0)^2 - w_d(d^2 - dd_0 \cos(2\phi) + d_0^2)] r + \frac{1}{2} \lambda_a r + \lambda_v \frac{3}{4} r^2 \sin \psi \\ + \frac{\lambda_h}{4} \left(\frac{\sin \psi}{r} + \psi_l \right) r + \frac{\lambda_d}{4} \left(\frac{\sin \psi}{r} - \psi_l \right) r + \lambda (r_l - \cos \psi). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Below we consider the case where for simplicity $w_d = 0$, and $h_0 = d_0 = 0$. Inclusion of terms that consider nonzero values of the above constants is straightforward. The simplified Lagrange function is

$$\mathcal{L}(r, \psi, \psi_l, r_l) = \frac{r}{2} h^2 + \frac{r}{2} \lambda_a + \frac{3}{4} \lambda_v r^2 \sin \psi + \frac{r}{2} \lambda_h h + \frac{r}{2} \lambda_d d + \lambda (r_l - \cos \psi). \quad (\text{A.8})$$

A.3. Variation with respect to ψ and ψ_l

The EL equation is

$$\frac{d}{dl} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \psi_l} \right) - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \psi} = 0. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

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$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \psi} = rh \frac{\partial h}{\partial \psi} + \frac{3}{4} \lambda_v r^2 \cos \psi + \frac{r}{2} \lambda_h \frac{\partial h}{\partial \psi} + \frac{r}{2} \lambda_d \frac{\partial d}{\partial \psi} + \lambda \sin \psi, \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \psi_l} = rh \frac{\partial h}{\partial \psi_l} + \frac{r}{2} \lambda_h \frac{\partial h}{\partial \psi_l} + \frac{r}{2} \lambda_d \frac{\partial d}{\partial \psi_l}, \quad (\text{A.11})$$

where

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial \psi_l} = -\frac{\partial d}{\partial \psi_l} = \frac{1}{2}. \quad (\text{A.12})$$

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial \psi} = \frac{\partial d}{\partial \psi} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\cos \psi}{r}. \quad (\text{A.13})$$

Inserting Eqs.(A.12) and (A.13) into the expressions for $\partial \mathcal{L}/\partial \psi$ and $\partial \mathcal{L}/\partial \psi_l$, and using the definitions of h and d , yields

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \psi_l} = \frac{1}{4} (\sin \psi + \chi) + \frac{1}{4} (\lambda_h - \lambda_d) r \quad (\text{A.14})$$

where

$$\chi = r \psi_l, \quad (\text{A.15})$$

so that

$$\frac{d}{dl} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \psi_l} \right) = \frac{1}{4} (\cos \psi \psi_l + \frac{d\chi}{dl}) + \frac{1}{4} \cos \psi (\lambda_h - \lambda_d) \quad (\text{A.16})$$

Combining Eqs.(A.9)–(A.16) yields after rearrangement

$$\frac{d\chi}{dl} = \frac{\sin \psi \cos \psi}{r} + 3\lambda_v r^2 \cos \psi + 2\lambda_d \cos \psi + 4\lambda \sin \psi. \quad (\text{A.17})$$

A.4. Variation with respect to r and r_l

The EL equation is

$$\frac{d}{dl} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial r_l} \right) - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial r} = 0. \quad (\text{A.18})$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial r} = \frac{1}{2} h^2 + rh \frac{\partial h}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{2} \lambda_a + \frac{3}{2} \lambda_v r \sin \psi + \frac{1}{2} \lambda_h h + \frac{r}{2} \lambda_h \frac{\partial h}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{2} \lambda_d d + \frac{r}{2} \lambda_d \frac{\partial d}{\partial r}, \quad (\text{A.19})$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial r_l} = \lambda, \quad (\text{A.20})$$

where

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial r} = \frac{\partial d}{\partial r} = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\sin \psi}{r^2} \quad (\text{A.21})$$

so that

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial r} = \frac{1}{8} \left(\psi_l^2 - \frac{\sin^2 \psi}{r^2} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \lambda_a + \frac{3}{2} \lambda_v r \sin \psi + \frac{1}{4} (\lambda_h - \lambda_d) \psi_l, \quad (\text{A.22})$$

$$\frac{d}{dl} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial r_l} \right) = \frac{d\lambda}{dl}, \quad (\text{A.23})$$

Inserting Eqs.(A.20) and (A.22) into Eq.(A.18) yields

$$\frac{d\lambda}{dl} = \frac{1}{8} \left(\psi_l^2 - \frac{\sin^2 \psi}{r^2} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \lambda_a + \frac{3}{2} \lambda_v r \sin \psi + \frac{1}{4} (\lambda_h - \lambda_d) \psi_l, \quad (\text{A.24})$$

or

$$\frac{d\lambda}{dl} = \frac{1}{8} \frac{(\chi^2 - \sin^2 \psi)}{r^2} + \frac{1}{2} \lambda_a + \frac{3}{2} \lambda_v r \sin \psi + \frac{1}{4} (\lambda_h - \lambda_d) \frac{\chi}{r}, \quad (\text{A.25})$$

We note that the combination $(\lambda_h - \lambda_d)$ appears only in the Euler–Lagrange equation for r , while it does not enter the corresponding equation for ψ . This reflects that the coupling between the mean curvature and deviatoric constraints acts through the radial geometry rather than the angular parametrization.

A.5. Principal part and ellipticity

We now extract the principal part of the reduced axisymmetric Euler–Lagrange system derived above and compare it with the ellipticity analysis of the full surface functional given in Section 2.2. Since in this Appendix we have specialized the axisymmetric Lagrangian to the case $w_d = 0$ and $h_0 = d_0 = 0$, the calculation below addresses the isotropic sector of the theory and provides a reduced axisymmetric consistency check rather than an independent derivation of the full two-dimensional ellipticity criterion.

From Eq. (A.8), the only term containing the highest derivative is the bending contribution

$$\frac{r}{2} h^2, \quad h = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\sin \psi}{r} + \psi_l \right).$$

Substituting the expression for h gives

$$\frac{r}{2} h^2 = \frac{r}{8} \left(\frac{\sin \psi}{r} + \psi_l \right)^2 = \frac{r}{8} \psi_l^2 + \frac{1}{4} \sin \psi \psi_l + \frac{1}{8} \frac{\sin^2 \psi}{r}.$$

Only the first term contributes to the principal part, since the remaining terms contain at most first derivatives.

Accordingly,

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \psi_l} = \frac{r}{4} \psi_l + \text{lower-order terms},$$

and therefore

$$\frac{d}{dl} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \psi_l} \right) = \frac{1}{4} (r \psi_l)_l + \text{lower-order terms} = \frac{1}{4} r \psi_{ll} + \text{lower-order terms}.$$

Hence the principal part of the reduced Euler–Lagrange equation for ψ is

$$\frac{1}{4} r \psi_{ll}.$$

Since $r > 0$ on a regular axisymmetric profile away from the poles, the coefficient of the highest derivative is positive. Thus the reduced axisymmetric operator is elliptic in the isotropic case considered in this Appendix.

This is consistent with the main-text analysis of the quadratic curvature kernel in Section 2.2. In the full surface formulation the ellipticity conditions are obtained from the eigenvalues of the quadratic curvature form, whereas in the present axisymmetric reduction only the reduced highest-order bending mode survives in the principal part. The appendix calculation therefore confirms that the explicit axisymmetric Euler–Lagrange equation has the expected positive second-order principal coefficient in the isotropic sector, in agreement with the full ellipticity analysis, while the full anisotropic two-dimensional criterion remains the one derived in the main text.

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Data availability

Raw data on the shape presented in Fig. 1 is published at Židanek, D., Kralj-Iglic, V. (2025). Coordinates of v0.95 elementary quantum shape (Version 1) [Data set], Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17898583.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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